

BEHAVIOUR OF CHLORONITROBENZENES WITH HYDRAZINE AND
HYDRAZINE DERIVATIVES. PART IX. NITROPHENYL-
HYDRAZINES AND THEIR HYDRAZONES

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Preparations of six substituted *o*-nitrophenylhydrazines by the replacement of nitro group with a hydrazino group have been described. These have been characterised by the preparation of hydrazones.

During a programme of research undertaken in this laboratory on the synthesis of substituted phenylhydrazines, several polynitrophenylhydrazines have been synthesised by taking advantage of the mobility of a halogen atom with hydrazine hydrate (Joshi and Deobra, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 34; 1952, 29, 46; 1957, 34, 14; Kapil and Joshi, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 417). But none of them was found suitable for the preparation of nitro heterocyclic compounds.

The present communication describes the preparation of six substituted *o*-nitrophenylhydrazines by the action of hydrazine hydrate on substituted dinitrobenzenes. The dinitrobenzenes required for this purpose, viz., 1-chloro-3:4-dinitro- (Mangini and Deliddo, *Gazzetta*, 1933, 63, 612), 1-bromo-3:4-dinitro- (Körner, *ibid.*, 1874, 4, 322), 1-iodo-3:4-dinitro- (Ullman and Bielecki, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 2179; Kapil, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4127), 1:2-dichloro-4:5 dinitro- (Holleman, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1920, 39, 446)- benzenes, 2-chloro-4:5-dinitro- (Morgen and Glover, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1702) and 2-iodo-4:5-dinitrotoluenes (Kapil, under publication), have all been prepared by the nitration of corresponding nitrobenzenes.

All the substituted *o*-nitrophenylhydrazines, prepared, are crystalline coloured compounds, sparingly soluble in cold alcohol, but soluble in hot alcohol and ethyl acetate. These react readily with carbonyl compounds, forming hydrazones which are sometimes even less soluble than the parent hydrazine, and possess characteristic melting points and can also be used for the characterisation of carbonyl compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL**

4:5-Dichloro-2-nitro-phenylhydrazine.—To a solution of 1:2-dichloro-4:5-dinitrobenzene (5 g.), in alcohol, twice the equivalent quantity of hydrazine hydrate was added dropwise with vigorous shaking. It was kept for about an hour, when the hydrazine derivative formed separated out. It was filtered, washed well with water, cold alcohol and recrystallised from ethyl acetate in orange-red needles (3 g.), m.p. 170° (Müller and Hoffmann, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1925, 111, 293, record m.p. 194°).

By adopting a similar procedure other substituted phenylhydrazines were prepared (Table III).

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**All m.p.s are uncorrected.

TABLE I

No.	Carbonyl compound.	5 - Chloro - 2 - NP*		5 - Bromo - 2 - NP*		5 - Iodo - 2 - NP*	
		M.P. Colour.	%Chlorine. Found. Calc.	M.P. Colour.	%Bromine. Found. Calc.	M.P. Colour.	%Iodine. Found. Calc.
1.	Benzaldehyde	171°	Red	182°	Red	210°	Red
2.	Salicylaldehyde	223°	"	234°(d)	"	231°	"
3.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	200°	Orange	215°	"	223°	"
4.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	226°	Red	202°	"	211°	Orange
5.	Anisaldehyde	183°	"	11.62	208°	211°	Orange
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	138°	Orange	11.07	147°	209°	Red
7.	Acetophenone	154°	Orange	12.26	145°	123°	Orange
8.	Benzophenone	247°	"	9.92	10.09	243°	Red

*NP denotes nitrophenylhydrazones.

TABLE II

*No.	M.P.	Colour ₁	4 :5-Dichloro-2-NP.		4-Methyl-5-chloro-2-NP.		4-Methyl-5-iodo-2-NP.	
			%Chlorine. Found. Calc.	M.P. Colour.	%Chlorine. Found. Calc.	M.P. Colour.	%Iodine. Found. Calc.	
1.	**228°	Red	22.73	22.90	199°	Red	12.13	12.26
2.	**238°	"	21.51	21.77	236°	"	11.51	11.62
3.	248°	"	21.65	21.77	235°	"	11.48	11.62
4.	275°	Chocolate	21.60	21.77	245°	Chocolate	11.54	11.62
5.	228°	Red	20.74	20.88	201°	Red	10.95	11.11
6.	200°	Orange	19.86	20.00	175°	"	10.52	10.61
7.	171°	Red	21.82	21.91	153°	Red	11.39	11.69
8.	**260°	Orange-yellow	18.27	18.39	240°	Orange	9.53	9.71

*The number of the carbonyl compounds corresponds to those in Table I.

**Prepared before and the m.p.'s are 184°, 217° and 162° respectively.

TABLE III

No.	Halogenonitrobenzene used.	Phenylhydrazine formed.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	1-Chloro-3:4-dinitro-	*5-Chloro-2-nitro-	160°	Orange needles	C ₆ H ₄ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 18.72%	18.93%
2.	1-Bromo-3:4-dinitro-	*5-Bromo-2-nitro-	160°	„	C ₆ H ₄ O ₂ N ₂ Br	Br: 34.36	34.48
3.	1-Iodo-3:4-dinitro-	5-Iodo-2-nitro-	150°	Orange-red needles	C ₆ H ₄ O ₂ N ₂ I	I: 45.31	45.52
4.	1:2-Dichloro-4:5-dinitro-	*4:5 Dichloro-2-nitro-	170°	„	C ₆ H ₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	Cl: 31.64	31.98
5.	2-Chloro-4:5-dinitro-toluene	4-Methyl-5-chloro-2-nitro-	155°	„	C ₇ H ₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 17.52	17.61
6.	2-Iodo-4:5-dinitro-toluene	4-Methyl-5-iodo-2-nitro-	163°	„	C ₇ H ₅ O ₂ N ₂ I	I: 43.20	43.34

*Prepared before.

Phenylhydrazones were prepared in good yield by heating for half an hour a mixture of the substituted phenylhydrazine (0.2 g.) in alcohol (10 c.c.) and the carbonyl compound in equimolecular proportions in presence of 1 to 2 drops of glacial acetic acid. These were recrystallised from ethyl acetate. Characteristics of hydrazones prepared are shown in Tables I and II.

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